

The Canon

Quod jactatur

A Proposed Solution through the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System

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Abstract

The enigmatic canon *Quod jactatur*, attributed to Johannes Ciconia and preserved in the Modena manuscript MOe.5.24, f. 21v, has not yet found a fully satisfactory solution. Modern transcriptions, from Wolf (1900) onwards, share the same anomaly: the simultaneous superimposition of the three voices produces dissonances that are difficult to reconcile with the contrapuntal practice of the late Middle Ages.

The application of the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System makes it possible to identify the points of entry of the voices on the basis of the arrangement of the clefs, the enigmatic motto, and the other signs present in the manuscript. The analysis reveals a cyclic structure articulated into seven blocks of five *tempora*, in which the *contra* constitutes the generative voice, while the imitating voices, *triplum* and *tenor*, alternate active sections with sections of structural silence.

The solution proposed here presents *Quod jactatur* as a three-voice circular canon with a structural alternation of performing forces: consistently consonant

at structurally significant points and coherent with the contrapuntal technique of Ciconia's time.

Keywords: Johannes Ciconia; *Quod jactatur*; enigmatic canon; Ars subtilior; medieval counterpoint; polyphony; canonic imitation; reverse engineering; mensural notation; Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System.

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1. Introduction

Among the enigmatic canons of the late fourteenth century, *Quod jactatur* by Johannes Ciconia stands out for its lack of a universally accepted solution. The manuscript source is preserved in the Biblioteca Estense in Modena, ms. MOe.5.24, f. 21v (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Manuscript source preserved in Modena.

The canonic inscription transmitted by the manuscript prescribes a structure in which one voice serves as the theme, while two others imitate it at a regular distance of five *tempora*:

*Tenor quem contratenor triplumque fugant temporibus in quinque.*¹

The literal application of this prescription, however, gives rise to contrapuntal difficulties that have resisted every attempt at solution since the earliest modern transcriptions. The proposals by Johannes Wolf (1900), Charles van den Borren (1926), Willy Korte (1932), Suzanne Clercx (1960), Edward Stam (1970), and Margaret Bent and Anne Hallmark (1985) all produce dissonances, parallel motions, and vertical clashes that are difficult to reconcile with the contrapuntal practice of the late Middle Ages. What makes *Quod jactatur* particularly striking is that these problems are not evenly distributed: the two-voice combinations generally appear plausible, whereas the difficulties emerge only in the simultaneous superimposition of the three parts. Bent and Hallmark (1985) explicitly observed that the complete three-voice texture produces a degree of harshness that is difficult to justify.

The thesis advanced here is that the piece is indeed a canon for three simultaneously active voices, but that the entry of the *tenor* does not occur at the point traditionally assumed in the literature, but rather at the point of closure of the *contra* cycle.

¹The *tenor*, which the *contratenor* and the *triplum* pursue at a distance of five time-units.

This possibility emerges from a reverse-engineering analysis conducted through the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System, which makes it possible to identify both the sound matrix underlying the canon and the clef matrix, as will be illustrated in Section 4.

2. Historiography

Federico Ghisi (1942, p. 81) had already placed Ciconia's canons within the context of the imitative technique that developed from Machaut among Franco-Flemish composers up to Dufay, while also observing that this tradition found no comparable continuity in Italy after Ciconia himself.

Quod jactatur has been the subject of research and discussion for more than a century.

Although Ciconia's name appears in the Estense manuscript on the left, between the two staves, next to the decorated initial (Figure 1), the date of composition of *Quod jactatur* remains uncertain, and the issue is controversial in the specialist literature. It has nevertheless been observed that the piece differs from the other imitative canons of the fourteenth-century French secular repertory in the particular manner of entry of the voices, which do not enter at the unison or at the octave. Since imitative-canon procedures of this kind seem to have become established at a relatively late stage, it is thought that the piece may have been composed by Ciconia at the end of the Trecento, or in the early fifteenth century during his Paduan period.²

Stam (1970, pp. 164–166) proposed a comparison between *Quod jactatur* and Johannes Ockeghem's famous *Prenez sur moi votre exemple amoureux*, interpreting both as examples of polymorphic pieces capable of different modes of reading and performance. It is perhaps not irrelevant that in the Copenhagen *Chansonnier* (MS Thott 291 8, f. 39v) *Prenez sur moi votre exemple amoureux* presents several flats and several sharps simultaneously beside the clef, a notational device which recalls, at least visually, the ambiguity of the accidentals in *Quod jactatur* (Figure 2).

²Chessa (2002) dealt in particular with questions of dating.

Figure 2: Ockeghem manuscript in the Copenhagen *Chansonnier* (MS Thott 291 8, f. 39v).

None of the proposed solutions to *Quod jactatur*, considerable in number, has ever achieved general consensus. The difficulty does not stem from a simple problem of transmission, but from the very structure of the composition.

Johannes Wolf (1900) did not provide a complete three-voice transcription, transcribing only the voice notated in the manuscript. He indicated the order of entries only verbally: the *tenor* first, followed after five *tempora* by the *contra*, and after another five by the *triplum*.³ The question of the vertical superimposition of the three voices and of the resulting contrapuntal clashes was not addressed by him: Wolf implicitly left the complete realisation of the canon to the reader.

Charles van den Borren (1926) developed another three-voice solution in imitation at the fifth and acknowledged the presence of many dissonances, but interpreted them as a reflection of the stylistic audacity of the period.

Willy Korte (1932) likewise proposed a three-voice realisation, attributing the parallelisms and clashes to the greater contrapuntal freedom of fourteenth-century music.

Suzanne Clercx (1960) addressed the problem systematically, reading the opposing signs of flat and natural as different solmisation indications. By proposing two three-voice realisations of the canon at the fifth, she attempted to justify the errors of voice-leading by appealing, this time, to a principle that she considered characteristic of the French *Ars Nova*, according to which it was not necessary for all the parts to be simultaneously consonant, provided that the *tenor* maintained correct relations with each of the voices.

Edward Stam (1970) observed that some vocal combinations were more convincing than others and proposed four different three-voice *resolutiones*, varying the order of entries and the intervals of response. In none of them, however, was he able to eliminate the dissonances generated. Stam also recognised the cyclic character of the structure and intuited that the problems occurred above all in the first and last blocks, that is, around the point at which the circular canon turns back upon itself. Unlike the other editors, who adopt a modern transcription with a binary scansion, generally in 2/4 or 2/2, he took the expression *temporibus in quinque* as a metrical indication and constructed his transcriptions in 5/2, a solution that makes the distances between the entries and the block-like disposition of the polyphonic texture immediately legible, but which represents an editorial choice aimed at visualising

³“Der Bass beginnt, nach 5 Takten setzt der Alt, nach abermals 5 Takten der Sopran ein.” Wolf, *Der niederländische Einfluss in der mehrstimmigen gemessenen Musik bis zum Jahre 1480*, p. 208.

the structure rather than a feature deducible from the source.

The present discussion refers primarily to the critical edition by Margaret Bent and Anne Hallmark (1985, pp. 175–178). Although the two scholars continued to seek a simultaneous and complete three-voice solution, they explicitly recognised that only certain two-voice combinations were contrapuntally satisfactory, whereas the integral superimposition of the three parts produced a degree of harshness that was difficult to reconcile with the stylistic conventions of the repertory. In this context, they suggested that the functioning of the canon might depend on a cyclic organisation more complex than has generally been supposed.

Luciano Chessa (2002) regarded *Quod jactatur* as one of the earliest examples of a fifteenth-century enigmatic canon, deliberately constructed in order to conceal its own internal logic. In his study, the poetic text accompanying the notes appeared not as a mere rhetorical accompaniment, but as a genuine poetic statement in which the work deliberately declared its own artificial and elusive character. Chessa also stressed that the canon appeared to resist the most straightforward solutions.

More recently, Michele Epifani (2023) placed Ciconia’s canon within the broader category of *obscuritas* in the Italian *Ars Nova*, interpreting the enigmatic inscription and the anomalous key signature as deliberate manifestations of *subtilitas*.

In the present article, the rules of the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System are applied to the canon.⁴ In the proposed solution, described and justified in the following sections and published in the appendix, Ciconia’s canon belongs to the category of enigmatic canons. It is an instrumental structure that alternates two-voice and three-voice sections. The *contra* is the only part performed in its entirety as notated, whereas the *triplum* and *tenor* must be derived according to the indication given by the motto.

The trajectory of the various interpretations is summarised in Table 1 and ranges from the acceptance of the dissonances as a stylistic phenomenon, through the recognition of their anomalous character, to the suspicion—which finally approaches certainty—of a deliberate construction by means of enigmas.

⁴For a full description of the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System and of the sound and clef matrices employed in this study, see Bianchini (2026). The preprint is available on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18497758).

Author	Solution	Model	Main observations
Johannes Wolf	Successive entries every five <i>tempora</i> ; linear imitative interpretation	Complete three-voice simultaneity	Does not problematise the dissonances and takes for granted that the order of the voices in the manuscript coincides with the linear order of entries.
Charles van den Borren	Imitation at the fifth	Complete three-voice simultaneity	Identifies parallel fifths, octaves, and dissonances, but interprets them as stylistic audacities of the period.
Willy Korte	Simultaneous realisation based on the relation of the fifth	Complete three-voice simultaneity	Attributes the harmonic instability to the absence of a fully developed chordal conception in the fourteenth century.
Suzanne Clercx	Two alternative solmisation readings of a canon at the fifth	Complete three-voice simultaneity	States that the consonances function mainly in pairs and that the difficulties, which emerge in the complete simultaneous superimposition, are justified by the compositional technique of the time.
Edward Stam	Four different <i>resolutions</i> varying the order of entries and the intervals	Complete simultaneity with a cyclic three-voice structure	Recognises that some vocal combinations function better than others and identifies the cyclic character of the problem, but does not eliminate the global contrapuntal collisions.
Margaret Bent & Anne Hallmark	Critical analysis of previous solutions; invertible counterpoint	Problematic complete three-voice simultaneity	Two-voice combinations regarded as plausible; complete simultaneity produces harshness and parallels that are difficult to justify.
Luciano Chessa	Hermeneutic interpretation of the enigmatic canon	Deliberately ambiguous complete three-voice simultaneity	Shifts the problem from the technical plane to the poetic and symbolic one; conceives the canon as an intentionally obscure device.
Michele Epifani	Reading of the canon as <i>obscuritas</i> and <i>subtilitas</i>	Formally regular but enigmatic complete three-voice simultaneity	Emphasises the structural regularity of the <i>dux</i> and the deliberately artful character of the signature and inscription.
Luca Bianchini	The canon is enigmatic and has a cyclic block structure, produced by a combined and coherent system of sound and clef matrices	Regular structure alternating two- and three-voice sections	Identifies a cyclic system of two and three instrumental parts, built on Pythagorean matrices organised according to the prescriptions of the enigmatic motto.

Table 1: Principal modern interpretations of *Quod jactatur*.

3. Analysis of the Manuscript

Any solution of the canon must account for the elements explicitly present in the manuscript, first and foremost the three C clefs. The first, placed at the centre of the staff, is on middle C and corresponds to the modern alto clef; the other two are placed respectively on G (the fifth line above, read in alto clef) and on F (the first line below, read in alto clef), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Detail of the clefs and signs in the Modena manuscript.

In almost all transcriptions, the last two clefs serve to indicate the entries of the two voices at the distance of a fifth.

According to the literal interpretation, the *dux* must begin on C, as the central voice, and the melody must be played in its entirety exactly as Ciconia notated it in the manuscript. The subsequent replies begin respectively on G (the upper voice) and on F (the lower voice).

Beside each of the three clefs there also appear a natural sign and a flat sign, either in this same order or reversed, signs that most probably have to do with the rules of solmisation. Both G and F may be called *Ut* in hexachordal theory. The two additional C clefs, placed on G and on F, are therefore perfectly consistent with the musical theory of Ciconia's time.⁵

⁵According to Guidonian theory, the letters G and F, which for us are simply G and F, may

The central voice—the *contra*—constitutes the central part of the solution. It is answered by two further voices: one at the upper fifth, beginning on G (*triplum*), and one at the lower fifth, beginning on F (*tenor*), at a distance of five *tempora* from the *contra*, as specified in the text of the canon.

If the central part is to be performed in its entirety as notated, the other two are subject to the specific rules of the enigmatic canon, which must first be deduced from the verses placed beneath the musical notation.

4. The Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System

When *Quod jactatur* was tested by means of the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System, as described in the present author’s theoretical study (Bianchini (2026)), the initial aim was to determine how many realisations were compatible with the data provided by the manuscript, and for how many voices, independently of the title and of the text placed beneath the notes. For a fuller discussion of the System used here, I refer the reader to the preprint available on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18497758).

4.1 Specifications

The Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System is a generative model for canonic counterpoint founded on three distinct and interacting structural levels: the **sound matrix** (M_S), the **clef matrix** (M_K), and the **time matrix** (M_T). The analysis of *Quod jactatur* mainly employs the first two.

The Abstract Seed

The system formalises contrapuntal structures starting from a minimal numerical sequence, called the **Abstract Seed**. The numbers 1, 3, and 5 do not indicate absolute pitches, but relational positions within a diatonic structure: horizontally, they define a melody by successive thirds; vertically, they define the fundamental triad; diagonally, with a temporal displacement between the voices, they generate the canon.⁶

take different names depending on the position of the semitone, the direction of the scale, and the context. G may be called Sol, Re, or Ut, while F may be called Fa or Ut, although it always indicates the same pitch.

⁶The values 1, 3, and 5 do not designate absolute pitches or fixed positions within the scale, but relational positions within an intervallic structure: root, third, and fifth. This structure is not a modern analytical invention, but constitutes one of the elementary nuclei of Western diatonic

The Sound Matrix and the Unique-Pair Law

The sound matrix is constructed by arranging the Seed in staggered rows, one for each voice. The necessary and sufficient condition for avoiding parallel octaves and fifths—the two forbidden errors adopted as the only general constraint—is that each pair of adjacent values in the sequence (*bigram*) be unique: if the pair $1 \rightarrow 3$ occurs once, it cannot occur a second time in the same sequence. With only the values 1, 3, and 5 there are exactly nine possible pairs. A canon for N voices requires $N - 1$ internal transitions, all distinct. It follows that the maximum number of voices that can be handled with a single circular Seed is eight: seven internal transitions plus the closure of the cycle, with exactly 24 valid configurations out of 560 theoretically possible permutations of the multiset 1, 1, 1, 3, 3, 3, 5, 5.

The Clef Matrix and Modular Reduction

The sound matrix defines the abstract intervallic structure, but does not yet assign concrete pitches. For this purpose, the clef matrix is applied, derived from the Pythagorean table (the common multiplication square) and reduced in modular arithmetic modulo 7. The mod 7 reduction is justified by the fact that there are seven diatonic notes: the value 7 corresponds to the octave (structural identity), 8 to the simple second, and so forth. Applying the clef matrix means adding, column by column, the values of the sound matrix to the corresponding transposition values: each row of the modular Pythagorean table generates a canon at a different interval (row 1 produces a canon at the upper second, row 2 at the third, row 4 at the fifth, and so on).

Inverse Application (*Reverse Engineering*)

The system may also be used analytically, starting from an existing composition. Given a melodic theme, the structural degrees of each block are extracted (the values 1, 3, and 5 in the first bar of each segment), the succession of roots is reconstructed,

harmony in its historically most widespread form. The possible presence of a seventh, ninth, or eleventh does not invalidate this basic level: a ninth can be defined as such only in relation to a root assumed as 1; if the point of reference changes, the same pitch may assume a different intervallic function. The designation of a note as 1, 3, or 5 therefore depends on a conventional choice of normalisation: the transposition of the label does not modify the vertical relations between the voices or the structure of the successive imitations, which remain determined by the melody of the *dux* and by the interval of response. For the purposes of the analysis, what matters is the structural relation 1–3–5, not the absolute name attributed to the starting point.

and the corresponding sequence of clef-anchors is derived. If this sequence corresponds to a row of the modular Pythagorean table, the structure is canonically generated by the system. The verification of the absence of palindromy in the clef matrix makes it possible to exclude retrograde solutions; the regularity of the temporal blocks also excludes canons by augmentation.

Relevance to the Case of *Quod jactatur*

In Ciconia's canon, the structural analysis reveals seven blocks of five bars each, with roots following the succession A–E–B \flat –F–C–G–D according to the circle of fifths. The corresponding clef matrix produces the transposition values +0, +4, +1, +5, +2, +6, +3, which can be verified on the modular Pythagorean table. It is this structure that determines both the circular nature of the canon and the contrapuntal incompatibilities at the point of closure of the cycle, as illustrated below.

4.2 Analysis

The stages of the analysis are summarised here.

1. Identification of the generative theme. The theme is immediately recognisable, since it is written in the central C clef (alto clef) and serves as the point of reference for the entire canonic construction.
2. Observation of the general structure. The canon presents a circular form, as indicated by the presence of the *custos*, and is divided into seven blocks.
3. Verification of the cyclic closure. At the end of the last block, the *custos* leads back to the same initial pitch, indicating that the cycle closes exactly upon itself.
4. Normalisation of the temporal structure. The values have been organised into equivalent 2/4 bars in order to highlight the internal symmetries of the composition.
5. Determination of the length of the blocks. The 35 bars as a whole are exactly divisible by 7, the number of blocks, and therefore each block consists of 5 bars.
6. Extraction of the structural degrees. In each five-bar block, the degrees 1, 3, and 5 have been identified, excluding for simplicity the degrees 7, 2, and 4, according to the model of the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System. Figure 4

shows this procedure applied to entire five-bar blocks: for example, the 1 of the first block is A, the root of the A–C–E triad arranged horizontally, whereas the 1 of the third block is B♭, likewise the root of the B♭–D–F triad.

Figure 4: Example of extraction of the degrees.

7. Reconstruction of the roots of each block. From the analysis of the degrees, the root associated with each block was deduced: in the example shown in Figure 4, this is A for the first block and B♭ for the third.
8. Analysis of the relations between roots. The regular succession A–E–B♭–F–C–G–D is obtained through successive transpositions by fifth. It follows that the canon is at the upper fifth.
9. Reconstruction of the clef matrix. Starting from the succession of roots, the corresponding matrix of Pythagorean clef-anchors was derived, governing the structure of the entire canon. In the case of *Quod jactatur*, it is formed by the numbers 0, 4, 1, 5, 2, 6, 3, which must be added to the degrees 1, 3, or 5 in order to find the actual note. In Figure 4, the 1 of the first block is equal to $1 + 0 = 1$ (A), the 1 of the second block is equal to $1 + 4 = 5$ (E), and the 1 of the third block is equal to $1 + 1 = 2$ (B♭). Since the first block has A as its root, its degree 3 corresponds to C: it is precisely from this C, indicated by the central clef of the manuscript, that the melody entrusted to the *contra* begins.
10. Verification of the symmetries. Since the clef matrix 0, 4, 1, 5, 2, 6, 3 does not present a palindromic structure, it was possible to exclude the hypothesis that the canon is retrograde.
11. Analysis of the time matrix. The regular division into groups of five bars also excluded the possibility that the canon is augmented or diminished.
12. Analysis of the sound matrix. The disposition of the degrees and of the intervallic successions proved incompatible with a retrograde-inverse or mirror

construction, since inversion or mirror symmetry would otherwise have been visible in the right and left halves of the matrix.

13. Determination of the number of voices. The superimposition of the blocks transposed at the fifth was possible only for three blocks at a time. The canon is therefore for three voices. The addition of a further fourth voice at the upper fifth would in fact introduce into the sound matrix pairs of values that would systematically generate tritones, unisons, or parallelisms, as illustrated for example in Figure 5.

The figure shows a musical score for four voices: Quadruplum, Triplum, Contra, and Tenor. The score is divided into four blocks (BLOCCO 1-4). Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Dissonances are highlighted in red.

Block	Quadruplum	Triplum	Contra	Tenor
BLOCCO 1	3	3	3	3
BLOCCO 2	5	1	3	6
BLOCCO 3	3	6	3	3
BLOCCO 4	3	1	5	5

Figure 5: Addition of the *quadruplum*. The dissonances are highlighted in red.

14. Critical issue. In three voices, the sixth and seventh blocks prove incompatible with the first from the point of view of the sound matrices, producing dissonances and parallelisms at the point of return of the cycle.

The analysis of the simultaneities generated by the canonic solution with imitation at the fifth and an interposed *contra* shows a non-random distribution of contrapuntal conflicts (parallelisms and dissonances). Assuming the position of the *contra*, explicitly indicated by the manuscript, to be correct, the principal problems always emerge precisely in connection with blocks 6 and 7 when these are assigned to the two outer voices. Block 6 of the *triplum*, in simultaneity with block 1 of the *tenor*, produces two full bars characterised by successions of parallel seconds lacking adequate resolution (Figure 6).

Figure 6 shows a musical score for three voices: Triplum, Contra, and Tenor. The Triplum part is labeled 'BLOCCO 6' and the Tenor part is labeled 'BLOCCO 1'. The score consists of five measures. The Triplum part has a treble clef and a 7/8 time signature. The Contra part has a treble clef and a 7/8 time signature. The Tenor part has a bass clef and a 7/8 time signature. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Dissonances between the outer voices are highlighted in red.

Measure	Triplum	Contra	Tenor
1	3	1 1	3
2	6	1	5
3	5	5	3
4	3	6	3
5	5	1 1 6	1

Figure 6: Block 6 of the *triplum* against block 1 of the *tenor*. The dissonances between the outer voices are highlighted in red.

Similarly, block 7 of the *triplum* against block 2 of the *tenor* generates two parallel octaves and a dissonance on the strong beat that finds no convincing justification in the contrapuntal practice of the period (Figure 7).

Figure 7 shows a musical score for three voices: Triplum, Contra, and Tenor. The Triplum part is labeled 'BLOCCO 7' and the Tenor part is labeled 'BLOCCO 2'. The score consists of five measures. The Triplum part has a treble clef and a 7/8 time signature. The Contra part has a treble clef and a 7/8 time signature. The Tenor part has a bass clef and a 7/8 time signature. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Dissonances between the outer voices are highlighted in red.

Measure	Triplum	Contra	Tenor
1	1 1	3	3
2	1	5 3	1
3	5	3	6
4	6	1	6
5	1 1 6	3 1	1

Figure 7: Block 7 of the *triplum* against block 2 of the *tenor*. The dissonances between the outer voices are highlighted in red.

Problems are also found in the combinations between block 4 of the *triplum* and block 6 of the *tenor*, and between block 5 of the *triplum* and block 7 of the *tenor* (Figure 8).

Figure 8 is a musical score for three voices: Triplum, Contra, and Tenor. The score is divided into three measures. The Triplum part is labeled 'BLOCCO 5' and has fingerings 3, 3, 1, 6, 5, 1, 3, 1. The Contra part is labeled 'BLOCCO 6' and has fingerings 3, 6, 5, 3, 5, 1. The Tenor part is labeled 'BLOCCO 7' and has fingerings 1, 1, 1, 5, 6, 1, 1, 6. Red dots highlight dissonances between the outer voices (Triplum and Tenor) in the second and third measures.

Figure 8: Problematic combinations involving blocks 6 and 7 of the *tenor*. The dissonances between the outer voices are highlighted in red.

Further dissonances occur between block 6 and block 1 in their respective cyclic superimpositions (Figure 9).

Figure 9 is a musical score for three voices: Triplum, Contra, and Tenor. The score is divided into three measures. The Triplum part is labeled 'BLOCCO 6' and has fingerings 3, 6, 5, 3, 5, 1. The Contra part is labeled 'BLOCCO 7' and has fingerings 1, 1, 1, 5, 6, 1, 1, 6. The Tenor part is labeled 'BLOCCO 1' and has fingerings 3, 5, 3, 3, 1, 3, 1. Red dots highlight dissonances between the outer voices (Triplum and Tenor) in the second and third measures.

Figure 9: Cyclic superimposition of block 6 and block 1. The dissonances between the outer voices are highlighted in red.

In all these cases, extended successions of parallel dissonances or parallel octaves appear, continuing for several consecutive beats: sequences of two or more contiguous notes in dissonant parallel motion, or dissonances that fall on strong beats without immediate resolution. The significant point is that these anomalies are concentrated exclusively in blocks 6 and 7. As for the other blocks, the simultaneous combinations are instead compatible with Ciconia's contrapuntal language. The remaining dissonances are in fact isolated, local, and regularly resolved through the motion of the parts, without generating chains of parallel dissonances or persistent structural collisions (Figure 10).

The image shows a musical score for three voices: Triplum, Contra, and Tenor. The score is divided into five blocks labeled BLOCCO 2, BLOCCO 3, and BLOCCO 4. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-6. Red dots highlight specific dissonances between the outer voices (Triplum and Tenor) in the first and fifth blocks.

Figure 10: Block 3 in the *contra*. The isolated and resolved dissonances between the outer voices are highlighted in red.

The distribution of the conflicts therefore does not appear random, but is consistent with the hypothesis that blocks 6 and 7 correspond to the tacet sections of the outer voices. From this perspective, their absence from the principal superimpositions between *tenor* and *triplum* does not represent an arbitrary editorial choice, but rather a direct consequence of the distance of five plus five *tempora* between the entries of the voices.

The results of the analysis reveal a three-voice canon, constructed by imitation at the fifth and with entries separated by five *tempora*. The contrapuntal conflicts observed at the point of closure of the cycle are concentrated in the last two blocks. It follows that blocks 6 and 7 of the *contra* must be excluded from the imitations of the *triplum* and the *tenor*.

5. Proposed Solution

5.1 The Motto

The three-voice anomaly of the last two blocks constitutes the starting point of the subsequent investigation and brings into play other signs in the manuscript, most notably the text.

The canon has a text, but this text is not sung, since the usual division into syllables is lacking.⁷ The piece therefore presents itself as an instrumental work, whose motto

⁷Epifani stresses that “Il copista sembra aver optato per disporre parole intere, più che singole sillabe, con risultati spesso ambigui. Situazioni simili sono piuttosto rare per il Trecento, e ciò potrebbe indurre a sospettare che, più che a un testo da declamare, ci si trovi di fronte a un paratesto indebitamente promosso a testo; d’altro canto, per brani a tradizione unitestimoniale

is a paratext functioning as an enigma.⁸ This use does not appear foreign to the musical culture in which Ciconia is situated. As Nádas (1980) observes, the composer belongs to a historical phase characterised by considerable intellectual elaboration of compositional and notational techniques, within which the musical enigma constitutes a well-documented practice:

*Quod jactatur et virtus opere non demonstratur. Ut aqua pissis saepius scientia denegatur.*⁹

By alluding to fish, which are notoriously mute, and to virtue, which must never show itself publicly as an act of vainglory, the motto appears to suggest that certain parts of each response are not to be played.

5.2 The Order of the Voices

The first voice, as indicated by the position of the first central clef, is the *contra* and not the *tenor*, as in most modern transcriptions. The *contra* sounds the entire notated melody, and to it respond the other two voices: the *triplum* above and the *tenor* below.

The two corresponding clefs on G and F are placed exactly in vertical alignment with one another and at the same distance from the central clef. The structure is deliberate, since it is reiterated on the second staff of Figure 3, as if to underline its prescriptive character.

5.3 Five *Tempora*

In the motto it is written that the voices pursue the tenor at a distance of five *tempora*.

A necessary and sufficient condition for the *contra* to pursue the tenor, which lies five *tempora* before the point of departure, is that the canon be circular and therefore traversable in both directions.

come questo, è difficile stabilire dove finisce l'oscurità deliberatamente perseguita dall'autore e dove inizi l'arbitrio del copista" (Epifani 2023, p. 105).

⁸According to (Stam, 1970, p. 156) as well, the text *Quod jactatur* would constitute a complement to the canonic inscription and would suggest an exclusively instrumental destination for the piece.

⁹What is boasted of, and virtue itself, are not shown in the work. As the fish in water, so knowledge is often concealed.'

Quod jactatur is so, since at the end of the musical line of the *contra* the final *custos* is marked, referring the melody back to the beginning and causing it to repeat potentially ad infinitum, as may be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Detail of the *custos*, which obliges the *dux* to return cyclically upon itself.

In an infinite, or circular, canon containing imitations other than at the unison or the octave, and returning each time exactly upon itself, the blocks must as a rule be equal and seven in number, or a multiple of seven, in order to complete the full cycle of the seven diatonic transpositions and return to the initial position without omitting or repeating any of them.¹⁰ In the case of *Quod jactatur*, with imitation at the upper fifth, the seven blocks of five bars traverse the entire cycle of fifths (A–E–B \flat –F–C–G–D) before returning to the initial position, that is, to A, as shown in Table 2.

¹⁰Each new entry of the canon is transposed by a fifth in relation to the preceding one. In the diatonic system this means advancing by four degrees at a time: A→E→B \flat →F→C→G→D→A. The return to the point of departure occurs only after all seven degrees of the scale have been traversed, which is why the minimal structure of the cycle consists of seven blocks.

Block	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	...
Initial bar	1	6	11	16	21	26	31	36	...
Degree	A	E	B \flat	F	C	G	D	A	...

Table 2: Canon at the upper fifth with blocks of five bars. The seven blocks of the *contra* notated in the manuscript are shown in red. After seven blocks ($5 \times 7 = 35$ bars), at the thirty-sixth bar the system returns to its initial position.

Ciconia does not invent the canonic structure from scratch, but adopts one already well established in the tradition of medieval circular canons.¹¹ Within the constraints adopted in this study, the structure admits only one configuration compatible with the cyclic return to the same pitch, independently of the antiquity of the piece or the composer’s mastery. A circular canon obeys mathematically pre-established laws, which are reflected precisely in the word canon: law, rule. Any composer wishing to construct an infinite canon at the fifth, or at another interval other than the octave or the unison, while preserving the same note at the beginning of each cycle, must conform to them.

The seven-block structure is not an innovation by Ciconia, but the result of a structural necessity. If there had been six blocks, the cyclic return would not have led back to the initial note, but would have shifted the system onto a different degree of the circle of fifths, causing the *contra* to begin again on F instead of C (Table 3).

Triplum		1	2	3	4	5	6	1	...
Contra	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	...
Tenor						1	2	3	...
Bar	1	6	11	16	21	26	31	36	...
Degree	A	E	B \flat	F	C	G	D	A	...

Table 3: In the six-block circular canon, the first block lies a fifth below.

¹¹Edward Stam (1970, p. 151) interprets the presence of seven segments as a particular solution devised by Ciconia in order to allow the closure of the canonic circle, and hypothesises that the composer may have settled on this number only while writing the final segments. In reality, the number seven does not derive from a free choice on the composer’s part, but from a general property of any infinite canon constructed through successive transpositions by fifth and intended to return to the same initial pitch. Under such conditions, the completion of the full cycle of the seven diatonic fifths constitutes a preliminary structural constraint, not a solution devised in the course of composition. The problem of the closure of the cycle therefore does not arise suddenly in the final segments, but is already implicitly solved at the very moment when one decides to construct a circular canon at the fifth intended to return indefinitely to its own point of departure.

One property of the circular canon is that, in order to function, it may begin from any block. Since in *Quod jactatur* the voice to be imitated is the *contra*, which begins from the first block, the valid points of departure are the first C of the *contra*, the G of the *triplum*, and the F of the *tenor*. These three points are at a distance of five *tempora*—measured here as 2/4 bars—from the *contra*, as shown in Table 4.

-5	0	+5
		triplum
	contra	
tenor		

Table 4: Entries of the two voices at a distance of 5 *tempora*. The *triplum* follows the *contra*, whereas the *tenor* precedes it by five *tempora*.

If the *contra* begins on C, which is the third above the root A, the *triplum* responds to it by imitating what the *contra* has done a fifth higher, that is, from G. At the seventh block, at a distance of five *tempora* from the *contra*, the *tenor* takes up the theme of the *contra*, but this time beginning from F. The whole process repeats indefinitely, and each block rises by a fifth in relation to the preceding one, according to a circular Pythagorean succession, as shown in Table 5.

Triplum		1	2	3	4	5			1	...
Contra	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	...
Tenor							1	2	3	...
Bar	1	6	11	16	21	26	31	36	41	...
Degree	A	E	B \flat	F	C	G	D	A	E	...

Table 5: In the circular canon, the points of entry of the three voices are marked in red. The blocks of the *contra* are numbered from 1 to 7, those of the *tenor* and the *triplum* from 1 to 5. If the cell is empty, the block is *tacet*.

The blocks pass from voice to voice, rising by a fifth. Since the canon is enigmatic, the voices that respond to the *tenor* will modify certain blocks by silencing some of them: the 10 bars of rest that precede the entries of the *triplum* and the *tenor* are the sum of two groups of 5 *tempora* and do not derive from the motto but from the structure, as shown in Table 6

Triplum		1	2	3	4	5			1	2	3	4	5			1	...
Contra	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	...
Tenor							1	2	3	4	5			1	2	3	...

Table 6: In the circular canon, the possible points of entry are marked in red. The blocks of the *tenor* and *triplum* imitate those of the *contra*, except in the sixth and seventh blocks, where the voices remain mute like the fish.

5.4 Fish and Virtue

The cyclic structure of the canon raises a precise technical problem. At the point of return, the sixth and seventh blocks prove incompatible with the first at the level of the sound matrices, producing irreparable dissonances and parallelisms if all three voices were to sound simultaneously, as has been shown from Figure 9 onwards.

This is not a defect of the composition, but a necessary consequence of the geometry of the circle of fifths: circular canons constructed through successive transpositions may encounter this tension at the point of closure of the cycle. The solution cannot be sought in the correction of the notes, but in the management of the entries.

The reason is as follows: the ten bars immediately preceding each entry reproduce material already present in one of the other voices at the same moment, generating parallelisms that would otherwise be irreparable. These bars must therefore be rendered silent. The *contra* is the only voice that performs all the blocks exactly as prescribed by the manuscript, whereas the other two withdraw in turn for ten *tempora*, the number required to constitute two blocks, one to the right and the other to the left of the *contra*.¹²

Since the two imitating voices behave symmetrically—what one does, the other does as well—the same principle applies to both. When the voice on G gives way to the voice on F, the latter sounds together with the *contra*; but when it is the turn of the voice on F to give way, it likewise omits the last ten bars of its own block, exactly as the voice on G had done. Silence is therefore not the prerogative of a single voice, but a structural rule governing both responses.

The association between the fish and that which remains hidden from sight already appears in the late-antique riddling tradition. The riddle *Flumen et piscis*, attributed to Symphosius, an author probably active around the fourth or fifth century, is in

¹²The counterpoint of *Quod jactatur* presents properties of invertibility: the voices could be combined at octave distances different from those proposed here, opening further possibilities of realisation that fall outside the aim of the present study.

fact based on the coexistence of the fish and the water that contains it without making it immediately visible.¹³ In this context, Ciconia’s reference to the *pissis* acquires particular relevance and seems to invite the reader to seek in the notation a solution that is not immediately manifest.

The enigmatic motto then ceases to be a poetic ornament and becomes an independent confirmation of a solution already obtained by structural means:

*Ut aqua pissis saepius scientia denegatur.*¹⁴

The fish imagery—mute creatures immersed in water—corresponds exactly to the behaviour of the imitating voices: present in the structure, but silent at the moments when their sound would generate conflict. Decisive here is the adverb *saepius* (‘often’, ‘frequently’): the text does not prescribe the permanent silence of a voice, but an *alternating* silence, which is precisely what the mathematical structure of the canon requires. The motto does not invent this solution: it names it.

The same idea is restated in the first verse, in which virtue—the theme—must not be displayed, but hides itself:

*Quod jactatur et virtus opere non demonstratur.*¹⁵

The canon therefore sounds complete in three voices for three blocks of fifteen *tempora*, while in the remaining four blocks the imitating voices alternately give way, allowing the *contra* to proceed uninterruptedly. Silence does not represent an absence of structure: it is the condition that enables the structure to function.¹⁶

¹³See Symphosius (400).

¹⁴The image of the fish is not isolated in the tradition of enigmatic canons. Schiltz documents, for example, the mottoes *Fit aries piscis in licanosypathon* and *In paripatheypaton aries vertatur in pisces*, used to indicate particular canonic transformations, respectively retrograde and retrograde-transpositional (Schiltz, 2015, pp. 396, 402). The recurrent presence of the fish in contexts of enigmatic solution suggests that this image may have performed a technical or allusive function within the culture of musical canons.

¹⁵‘What is boasted of, and virtue itself, are not shown in the work.’

¹⁶The use of structural silences as a constitutive element of musical construction is not foreign to late-medieval compositional practice. In her study of the *hockets* of the *Ars subtilior*, Zayaruznaya (2014) has shown how the programmed alternation of sound and silence may perform an essential organising function both compositionally and notationally. Although belonging to a context different from that of *Quod jactatur*, these observations show that silence could be conceived as an active component of musical structure, and not as a mere absence of sounding material.

5.5 Hexachords

It remains to consider the succession $\sharp\flat$ or $\flat\sharp$, which appears beside the clefs in the manuscript. For a theoretical framework of contextual solmisation and *musica ficta* in the late-medieval repertory, we refer to Bent (1984)¹⁷ and Berger (1987).

The simultaneous presence of a flat and a natural sign in the signature has given rise to various interpretative hypotheses, from the solmisation reading proposed by Clercx (1960) to Stam's hypothesis (1970) of a composition conceived for different modal configurations. According to Apel, cited by Chessa (2002, p. 417), the double signature served to indicate a flexibility in the intonation of the degree B, now as *B fa*, now as *B mi*, made necessary by the fact that strict imitation at the fifth would produce an augmented fourth in bar 8. The question thus remains unresolved in the existing literature.

In the present study, on the basis of the transcription in the appendix, we advance the hypothesis that the flats and natural signs placed differently beside the clefs serve to indicate different hexachordal fields.

It may be observed, for example, that when the *tenor* has not yet entered on F at the beginning of the canon, B is natural. At the same point, after the *tenor* has answered in the preceding block, the same natural becomes a flat in order to avoid the tritone, as shown in Figure 12.

The natural and flat signs indicate fluctuation within the hexachord between different states, depending on the cyclic combination of the voices active at that moment: according to whether the 1–3–5 sonority on C, F, or G is complete or incomplete, in an upper or lower position, the appropriate solmisation varies, since mutations have occurred within the hexachords.

6. Conclusions

The problem of *Quod jactatur* does not derive from a corrupt transmission of the musical text, nor from a presumed medieval tolerance towards systematic dissonances and parallel fifths, parallel octaves, or voice-leading parallels. The difficulties that

¹⁷On the basis of Bent's approach, the written letter should not be understood as a modern label of fixed pitch. In the case of the degree B, the distinction between *B fa* and *B mi* belongs to a functional system dependent on context; the decisive question, therefore, is not whether the modern editor should mechanically read B as a single predetermined pitch, but how the local contrapuntal situation determines its sounding realisation, especially in the presence of vertical perfect intervals.

The image shows two systems of musical notation for the 'contra' part. The first system starts at measure 1 and the second at measure 31. Each system consists of three staves: Triplum (top), Contra (middle), and Tenor (bottom). The Triplum staff is mostly empty with a few notes. The Contra staff contains the main melodic line with various rhythmic values and accidentals. The Tenor staff provides a harmonic accompaniment. Numerical annotations (3, 5, 3, 3, 1, 3, 1) are placed below the Contra staff, likely indicating fingerings or specific intervals. A 'Clef Matrix' and 'Sound Matrix' are indicated in the first system. The measure number '31' is written above the first staff of the second system.

Figure 12: Hexachordal mutation in the first block of the *contra*.

have accompanied the various transcriptions of the canon for more than a century arise rather from a reading of the clefs and of the enigmatic inscription that assumes from the outset a disposition of the voices different from that suggested by the manuscript.

The solutions proposed by Wolf, van den Borren, Korte, Clercx, Stam, Bent, and Hallmark differ significantly in detail, but all share the same presupposition: the search for a complete simultaneity of the three voices starting from an order of entry assumed to be self-evident. It is precisely this presupposition that generates the contrapuntal collisions which the literature has repeatedly observed without being able to eliminate.

The solution proposed here, by contrast, arises from an integrated rereading of all the elements present in the source: the disposition of the clefs, the distance of five *tempora* prescribed by the motto, the circular character of the composition, the final *custos*, the seven-block structure required by the cyclic return to the same pitch, and the very content of the enigmatic inscription. Considered together, these elements converge towards an internally coherent configuration.

The application of the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System makes it possible to reconstruct this configuration by means of a sound matrix and a clef matrix that describe the behaviour of the three voices within the cycle. From this perspective, the *contra* constitutes the generative voice, while the *triplum* and the *tenor* represent two transformations of the same structure. The result is a configuration consistent

with all the elements of the source, not an editorial choice.

Perhaps the most significant aspect is that the canon requires no stylistic exception in order to justify its contrapuntal difficulties. The dissonances that had led several scholars to invoke exceptional compositional freedoms, the audacities of the *Ars subtilior*, or particular medieval licences prove to be the direct consequence of a mistaken configuration of the voice entries. Once the correct disposition of the voices has been reconstructed, the contrapuntal fabric reveals a coherence that previous realisations were unable to explain.

This also entails a different interpretation of the enigmatic text. The verses no longer appear as a simple poetic accompaniment or as a literary ornament, but as an integral part of the compositional mechanism. The motto provides operational instructions for the management of the voices, their points of entry, and the zones of silence necessary for the structure to function. In this sense, the text does not comment on the canon: it helps to construct it.

The implications of the present study extend beyond the specific case of *Quod jactatur*. The analysis suggests that at least some of the problems posed by late-medieval enigmatic canons may depend not on errors of transmission or on imperfect compositional practices, but on the loss of the operational rules governing their realisation. If this is the case, modern musical editing may have interpreted as contrapuntal anomalies what were originally performance instructions or implicit constructive principles.

Quod jactatur should therefore not be regarded as a problematic case at the margins of the tradition, but as a remarkable example of cyclic canonic design transmitted by the medieval manuscript tradition. The work reveals a structural conception in which text, notation, disposition of the clefs, temporal organisation, and contrapuntal construction participate in a single project. The enigma does not consist in the arbitrary concealment of a solution, but in the ability to hide a rigorously coherent structure behind an apparent musical impossibility.

The proposed solution restores unity to elements that historiography had regarded as separate. The new disposition of the entries does not constitute one interpretative variant among many possible ones, but a direct consequence of the structural constraints imposed by the manuscript canon.

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I wish to thank Professor Margaret Bent for the material she kindly provided and for drawing my attention to *Quod jactatur* as a possible case study, suggesting that I verify whether the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System might offer useful elements for addressing some of the questions left open in the literature. Her objection to simultaneous three-voice realisations helped to direct the present investigation towards an alternative configuration. The interpretations and conclusions developed in this article are solely the responsibility of the author.

I also wish to thank Dr Anna Trombetta for her careful reading of the manuscript and for the numerous suggestions that helped to improve its clarity of exposition.

A. Appendix: Reconstruction of *Quod jactatur*

The present appendix contains the reconstruction of *Quod jactatur* documented in this study. The aim is to test operationally the hypotheses formulated above and to show that they produce a realisation consistent with the explicit elements of the manuscript.

The structure of the canon, organised into seven blocks of equal duration, each transposed a fifth higher than the preceding one, does not represent an arbitrary choice on the part of the composer, but is a necessary consequence of the cyclic nature of the system and of the return to the same initial pitch after completion of the full cycle of fifths.

In this solution, the *contra* constitutes the generative voice of the entire process, whereas the parts of the *triplum* and the *tenor* derive from the *contra* through the transformations indicated by the clefs and the motto.

The zones of silence (*tacet*) are functional components of the canonic mechanism and are consistent with the meaning of the enigmatic inscription.

Quod Jactatur

Canon

Realization by Luca Bianchini

Triplum

Clef Matrix

Contra

Sound Matrix

Tenor

6

11

16

Figure 13: Proposed reconstruction of *Quod jactatur* according to the model developed in the present study.

2

21

Musical notation for measures 21-25. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 21: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 5, 6, 5, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 22: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 6, 5, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 1; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 23: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 6; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 6, 5; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 24: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 5, 5, 6; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 1, 3, 1; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 25: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 6; Bass has a whole rest.

26

Musical notation for measures 26-30. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 26: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3, 1; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 6; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 27: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 1; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 5, 3; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 28: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 6, 5; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 5; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 29: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 1, 3, 1; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 1; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 30: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 6; Bass has a whole rest.

31

Musical notation for measures 31-35. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 31: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 1, 1; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 5, 3, 3, 1. Measure 32: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 1; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 1; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 5, 3, 3, 1. Measure 33: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 6, 5; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 6, 5; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1, 3, 1. Measure 34: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 1, 3, 1; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 1, 1, 6; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1. Measure 35: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 6; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 5, 3, 3, 1.

36

Musical notation for measures 36-40. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 36: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 5, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1, 6, 6, 1, 6. Measure 37: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 1; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingering 1; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1, 6, 6, 1, 6. Measure 38: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1, 6, 6, 1, 6. Measure 39: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1, 6, 6, 1, 6. Measure 40: Treble has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 3; Middle has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1; Bass has notes G4, A4, B4, C5 with fingerings 3, 1, 6, 6, 1, 6.

41

3 +4 5 3 3 1 3 1

3 5 5 3 3 3 1 1

46

3 +1 1 6 6 1 6

3 5 5 3 3 3 1 1

3 5 6 5 3 6 5 5 6

51

3 +5 5 3 3 3 1 1

3 3 6 5 3 6 5 5 6

3 3 1 6 5 1 3 1

56

3 +2 5 6 5 3 6 5 5 6

3 3 1 6 5 1 3 1

3

4

61

3 +6 3 1 6 5 1 3 1

3 6 5 3 5 1

66

3 +3 1 1 1 5 6 1 1 6

3 5 3 3 1 3 1

71

+0 3 5 3 3 1 3 1

3 1 6 6 1 6

76

3 +4 5 3 3 1 3 1 3 3

3 1 6 6 1 6 3 3

3 5 5 3 3 3 1 1 3 3

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